

Article

Restoring Bangladeshi Culture & Heritage through Museology and Conservation

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Abstract

This study examines the many roles that museums play in Bangladesh, with a particular emphasis on their roles as repositories of artefacts, hubs for research, and institutions for cultural preservation. The study explores the perceived problems museums face, try to give a sustainable potential solution, and the benefits of museum operations for community viability using primary research methods. It is anticipated that the results will add to the continuing conversations regarding museums' roles as promoters of cultural heritage and community growth.

Keywords: Museum, Bangladeshi museum, Conservation, Restoration, Heritage.

Introduction

In Bangla, museums can be addressed as "জাদুঘর" or "Jadughor" is literally the translation of 'Magic house' or "House of magic." The word 'culture' is also associated with museums and can designate songs, dancing, art, food, etc.

The term "museum" covers many things and is not all about where historical, cultural, artistic, and scientific objects are displayed. Because they offer a suitable setting for restoration, museums have a broad role in conservation. Nowadays, a lot of museums have backed community outreach and education initiatives. Future generations can have a clear picture of museums that can be brought and preserved for them, as well as our past. Unlike other nations, Bangladesh, as a multicultural society with many museums, protects its swaths of legacy.

Unfortunately, due to a lack of awareness, we are now losing most of our culture and heritage, which affects the present and can also affect our future generations understanding. So, we need to pay more attention to our museums because the museum is the best representation of culture and heritage.

Museum – the concept

The nine daughters of Zeus and Mnemosyne, who symbolize various artistic and scientific fields, are the traditional names for the Muses (Mojsik, 2023). Initially, the term museum was used to refer to places sacred to the 'Muses,' who associated glorious events, folk art, music, and poetry. These nine 'Muses' have appealing charm and find places in new museums, regardless of their modernity. The assemble places of museums can be categorizes into three places and are the first research and publication work, the storehouse phase, and the second phase, which involves caring for objects beyond exhibition grouping. The third phase involves planning material physical conditions in systematic galleries to attract and instruct public interest while focusing on educational agencies. The true conception of a museum depends on an art institution with educational uses and demands (Dwivadi, 1973).

The idea of a "museum" emerged from people's awareness of accumulating objects. The kings of Egypt and Mesopotamia had begun searching for riches as early as 2000 BC. Some of the historians believe that the first museum that has been discovered was the Ennigaldi Nanna's Museum. It was created in 530 BCE. It was situated in the Dhi Qar Governorate of modern-day Iraq, in Ur. It is also about 150 meters southeast of Ur's well-known Ziggurat. Archaeologists discovered that the dozens of artifacts, carefully organized side by side and ranging in age by centuries, were museum items when they unearthed particular areas of the

palace and temple complex at Ur. This was because the artifacts were accompanied by what was eventually identified as "museum labels". They were made of clay cylinder drums with three-language labeling. Princess Ennigaldi, the daughter of the final Neo-Babylonian Empire king Nabonidus, served as the curator. For all that the royal family had amassed, the museum served as storage for their private collection¹ (L, 2020).²

In the 18th century, there was a noticeable increase in the number of large public museums, including the British Museum in 1759 and the Louvre in 1793. These organizations were mostly born out of private collections, where the artwork was arranged in dense, balanced configurations that were thought by experts to provide a better assessment of different styles and trends. The Paris salons, where artwork was placed from floor to ceiling and paintings competed for space on the walls, also had an impact on them. These new public areas fascinated artists, and paintings from the early 19th century frequently included museum galleries (Li, 2020).

Museum development in Bangladesh

Bangladesh's first museum was the Varendra Research Museum (Islam S. M., 2023), which opened its doors in September 1910. The starting story of that museum begins by the establishment of Varendra Research Society, that was founded by the famous intellectuals such as, Ramprasad Chanda, Akshay Kumar Maitreya, and Kumar Saratkumar Ray. They began collecting artefacts out of a desire to conserve Bengal's history and culture, especially those of the Varendra region. Ray's efforts and this collection served as the museum's cornerstone. Lord Carmichael laid the foundation stone for a dedicated edifice in 1916, which was built with the Maharaja of Dighapatia's backing. The museum was originally established in 1919 and took on its current name, but its original name, "Varendra Anushandhan Samiti" (Varendra Investigation Society), reflected its research concentration (Rajshahi, n.d.). This museum showcased the area's prehistoric past and cultural artifacts, especially those with ties to the region's Muslim, Hindu, and Buddhist histories (Rashid, 2020).

¹ For all that the royal family had amassed, the museum served as storage for their private collection (L, 2020).

A phase of expansion and diversification came next. Basically, it is an organization for the preservation of the nation's cultural history was established in 1913 with the establishment of the Bangladesh National Museum (formerly known as the Dhaka Museum) (Ahmed, 1991). The mid-20th century saw the rise of specialized museums focusing on specific areas like folk art and the Liberation War (Rashid, 2020).³

Bangladesh has achieved considerable progress in the conservation of its museums, demonstrating a steadfast dedication to the protection of its extensive cultural heritage and historical narratives. Institutions such as Bangladesh National Museum, Ahsan Manzil serve to illuminate artefacts originating from ancient Bengal, colonial epochs, and the struggle for independence. Efforts towards preservation encompass restoration initiatives, systematic cataloging Public participation through interactive exhibitions and educational programs are frequently organized. In addition, regional museums like the Zainul Abedin Sangrahashala in Mymensingh have sprung up around the nation, concentrating on local history and culture (Khan, 2012).

Furthermore, Bangladesh endeavors to educate forthcoming generations and augment cultural tourism, thereby reinforcing national identity and collective pride. And further There are also plans to open community-based museums, encouraging local involvement in cultural preservation. To improve accessibility for a larger audience, technology is now being used increasingly for virtual tours and online collections, ongoing investment and heightened awareness are crucial for sustaining these initiatives amidst the environment and logistical challenges encountered (Khan, 2012)

Classification of museums in Bangladesh

Bangladesh is home to over 80 museums (an official figure is unavailable). That's more than enough for Bangladesh. these Museums can be classified into several types based on their focus and collections such as National Museums, Archaeological Museums, Ethnographic Museums, Science and technology Museums and Specialty Museums. So, having so much

² The mid-20th century saw the rise of specialized museums focusing on specific areas like folk art and the Liberation War (Rashid, 2020).

diversity we have classified three primary groups into which Bangladeshi museums fall and areas.

1. **Government-run Museums:** They are typically well-known museums. These records usually encompass a great deal of information on the history, culture, and legacy of a nation. They are mostly optimized and funded by the cultural ministry.

Examples: National Museum of Bangladesh and Liberation War Museum.

2. **Private or trust-run Museums:** They are comparatively less popular with people. Their collections are typically more specialized, reflecting the interests of the owner or founder. They are funded by neither individuals nor any trusted institution.

Example: Museum of Rajas and Abdul Karim's Museum.

3. **University Museums:** They frequently hold collections about the subject matter or area of study of the organization. Though the public may have access to its holdings, scholarly activities are frequently the main focus.

Example: Chittagong University Museum.

Problems in Bangladeshi Museums

Museums across Bangladesh grapple with a multitude of obstacles that impede their evolution and connection with the public. A significant number of these cultural institutions suffer from a dearth of financial support, resulting in neglected upkeep, antiquated displays, and inadequate preservation initiatives. Following are some problems which are nowadays facing these museums:

- **Lack of local interest in visiting museums:** In Bangladesh, museums may be found almost everywhere. These could be modest or big. Unfortunately, there was no interest in visiting the adjacent museum from the people. But tourists make up the bulk of visitors to any museum. Children are directly impacted by these. Since museums

are not introduced to children via their families or school curriculum, their lack of exposure is the root cause of their indifference in them.

- **Staff Shortage:** Effective operation of a museum necessitates a highly qualified staff; this issue has long plagued many museums. For an indefinite period of time, the post remains vacant when a museum employee retires or relocates. The most impacted museums are smaller, less well-known ones, which may be supported by trusts or the government, because filling them takes too long.
- **Inadequate conservator resources:** Every museum needs a conservator to guarantee the preservation of every object kept there. Professional conservation is necessary if you want anything to be kept for a long period. Many museums were devoid of conservators. Whenever a curator finds anything that needs to be added to the museum or conserved, they promptly inform "The National Museum of Bangladesh." To conserve the objects they want to keep, the National Museum will then send a conservator. On the other hand, conservators are not accepted at private museums. Instead of calling in conservators, they use alternate forms of treatment, including "Naphthalin,"
- **Inadequate restorer resources:** Restorers are essential to the preservation of museum items after restoration. In many Bangladeshi museums, especially the regional ones, there are unfortunately insufficient specialized restorers.
- **Insufficient practical training:** People start their careers at museums with a variety of educational backgrounds. They typically lack sufficient knowledge about the objects at museums. Most museum employees and curators were not trained to handle museum artefacts. Curators are given formal training related to their work. On the other hand, private museums did not provide any training space for its employees.
- **Underwhelming museum presentation:** The purpose of the museum's exhibits is to allow visitors to learn about the past. In order to learn more, they mostly read the employees there. Most of the

written material has unfortunately been removed. Furthermore, the lighting is inadequate to highlight the objects.

- **Absence of government oversight:** Most museums are under government control. Consequently, the government has responsibility for the museum's duties as well. Most museum curators are unable to act on behalf of the museum because they are not authorized to do so. This slows down the functioning process. Nonetheless, the government is ignoring the trust-sponsored museums. The great majority of museums that are privately or trust-funded are seeking government support.
- **Underfunding:** "Persistent underfunding of the museum sector in Bangladesh significantly restricts its ability to carry out its essential function in conserving and showcasing the country's rich cultural heritage. Inadequate funding leads to a number of problems, such as the degradation of priceless artefacts, a shortage of personnel, and restricted public access to exhibits. Future generations may thus be in risk of losing our cultural identity.

Solutions

Museums in Bangladesh face several challenges, yet solutions exist to help preserve and promote their cultural significance:

- **Educational benefits:** Our homes must be the first place we start. As was already said, there are museums in almost every part of Bangladesh. It might be small or big. Parents should visit museums with their kids at least once a year. Children will learn about the history of their community as a consequence. A visual depiction of history may help anybody better grasp the past, even though books and podcasts are also good ways to learn about it. Nonetheless, it could have a stronger impact on children's growth. A field trip to a museum ought to be part of the curriculum. Students will be able to see our past from a variety of angles thanks to it. All classes from fifth to tenth grade should contain an introduction to museum studies and an annual museum tour. Kids will find history more engaging with this method.

- **Address staffing shortages:** For a museum to function properly, a minimum number of members is needed. Every member has a certain duty. A member's post becomes empty for a considerable amount of time when they retire or transfer. Museum officials should schedule each member appropriately and cover the void in order to minimize a staffing shortage.
- **Invest in conservation:** An integral component of every museum is a conservator. because it is their duty to preserve and prolong the life of museum artefacts. To maintain items, every museum need hire a conservator. But for museums, especially private ones, it may be expensive. Government museums can, however, choose the conservators they choose according on their requirements. Alternatively, if hiring a conservator is too expensive, they can assign a committee of conservators to each region. This might potentially ensure the survival of all museums in that district, including government, private, and university museums.
- **Prioritize restoration:** A restorer is crucial to preserving museum artefacts. In the absence of their expertise, many antiquities would decay and vanish. Museum administrators could consider investing in staff training programs or employing local restorers to ensure the long-term preservation of valuable artefacts. Despite budgetary constraints, these strategies can help restore the authenticity of museum artefacts.
- **Professional training:** Managing a museum requires a team of people who have received the necessary training. Every object is delicate at a museum. Therefore, only people who have had a lot of training should handle them. For this reason, all museum curators ought to complete a minimum of twelve to twenty-four months of museology training. Every person who will be maintaining the artefact, including the curator, should get training relevant to their position.

- **Create engaging experiences:** In order to create a really captivating museum experience, it is essential to strike a balance between visually appealing displays and straightforward information. Incorporate strategies like long-lasting labelling materials, frequent maintenance, visitor-friendly display arrangement, and high-quality lighting fixtures. Museums may guarantee that visitors of all ages and abilities may thoroughly appreciate the items on display by emphasizing both item presentation and accessibility.
- **Empower private museums:** Most of the museums in Bangladesh are Government-run museums, although university and private museums are crucial to preserving the country's cultural legacy. Curators should have more decision-making authority from the government in order to enhance the overall condition of Bangladeshi museums.
- **Increased government attention:** Many Bangladeshi museums, both governmental and private, face limited financing and a scarcity of skilled staff. This has resulted in the degradation of priceless historical relics. To overcome these issues, the government should increase its attention for private museums while also investing in museum professional training and growth.
- **Diverse source of fund:** A multifaceted strategy to address underfunding will greatly help the museum sector in Bangladesh. A strong foundation cannot be established by increased government spending through special budgets and tax breaks. Since Bangladesh is still a developing nation, it is not a good idea to expect the government to aid. Therefore, since public-private partnerships may pool the resources of both sectors to finance certain projects, we can identify some more options. Creative methods of generating money, such corporate sponsorships, membership programs, crowdsourcing, and fundraising events, can bring in more money. Resource utilization may be maximized by enhanced management and efficiency brought about by professional leadership, financial transparency, and a variety of revenue sources. Digital platforms, interactive displays, education and outreach campaigns, and other public awareness and engagement efforts may encourage public support and draw tourists. Working together with museums throughout the world may help with resource mobilization, information exchange, and international exposure. Bangladesh can make sure that its rich cultural legacy is

preserved and promoted for next generations by combining these tactics.

Benefits and Impacts on Bangladeshi Society

The advantages and effects of diverse initiatives on Bangladeshi society are intricate, facilitating advancements in social, economic, and cultural realms. Programs dedicated to enhancing healthcare, education, and digital skills have elevated marginalized communities, alleviating poverty and enriching life quality.

Better museum management in Bangladesh why does it matter – a lot for heritage preservation, public involvement, money benefits and above all strengthening cultural identity. Museums can have a central role in safeguarding and promoting the diverse cultural heritage of Bangladesh through conservation, education, and engagement programs for all people. Using proper conservation methods and trained staff, a museum can add years on to their collection lives ensuring generations to come will have an opportunity study thing of their own. Well such museums can also contribute to a better understanding of Bangladeshi cultural heritage by presenting interesting and user-friendly exhibitions, educational programs and developing various activities. Good museums which are appropriately organized, can in addition serve as a major attraction for tourists, provide additional income to the locals and create jobs in tourism or cultural heritage. Museums can therefore contribute significantly to the strength of a nation's identity and unity and tend to foster community engagement as one gateway to cultural exchange by conserving and promoting the cultural heritage of Bangladesh.

Discussion

Museums are essential to preserve our nation's identity. We have discovered different kind of challenges as there is no conservator available in our museums only when something new add to the museum or start a new museum only that moment that arthurite informed National museum of Bangladesh then they send some one to conserve that particular object or the whole place. This preservation method only applies to government-

funded museums; non-government and private museums lack this facility because of insufficient funds. As well as conservation the same thing happening with restoration section. Mostly staffs are not going under through museology taring. Even the poor presentation making the museums unwelcomed. Insufficient financing also had an effect on our museums. Although, the local people did not show any interest on visiting museums that directly impacted on children.

As we know appointing conservator would be vary costly although there is not sufficient amount of certified conservator available here that's why we should appoint groups of conservators in each district that every museum (privet, govt, and university) could take the survives. But in restoration section one of museum staff could get trained as restorer that's how museums will get a permanent restorer. Although each and every member who will work for museum they all should goes under a professional taring according to their position. And all should focus on presentation and lighting. Because better presentation and lighting can showcase the artefect in best way. People should introduce museums to their kids to know better about the local and national history although school should add primary museum studies with their history class.

There are lot of beneficial impact on Bangladeshi society as it would be a great source to attract foreign currencies and could inspire entrepreneurs on tourism field.

Conclusion

According to the research's findings, a variety of delinquents in our museums have been dealing with them for a long time, which is harming the museum industry. Deficient conservators and restorers, inadequate taring, poor presentation, and a lack of funds all directly affect our heritage and museum sector. Implementing adaptable solutions is crucial to lessening this impact. These include a variety of funding sources to avoid relying on government assistance, specialized equipment to handle fragile items, and a team of conservators to assist a specific location. Despite this, Bangladesh will have a number of advantages, including the ability to draw in international investment, create a diversified workplace, and preserve our

cultural history through museums. More research ought to concentrate on the preservation of the Artefact at the Bangladeshi museum.

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